

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**TO COMPARE THE OUTCOME OF HEMORRHOIDECTOMY
BY LIGASURE WITH CONVENTIONAL MILLIGAN
MORGAN'S HEMORRHOIDECTOMY**Imam Bakhsh¹, Babur Murtaza², Saria Kiran³¹Basic Health Unit Akkan Wali District Bahawalnagar²Bahawalpur Victoria Hospital³Basic Health Unit 140/M District Bahawalnagar**Abstract:**

Objectives: The basic aim of the study is to compare the outcome of hemorrhoidectomy by LigaSure with conventional Milligan Morgan's hemorrhoidectomy. **Material and methods:** This cross sectional study was conducted in Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during February 2019 to July 2019. This study was conducted with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. There were total 100 patients which were included in this study. The patients were divided into two groups. Group A includes Haemorrhoidectomy by Ligasure and group B includes Milligan Morgan Haemorrhoidectomy by using the random allocation. The procedure was carried out with the patient in lithotomy position and a minor reverse Trendelenberg angle. **Results:** The data were collected from 50 patients which can be divided into two groups. The mean age of both groups were 40 to 60 years. Group A included 29 cases in which 20 were having 3rd degree haemorrhoids while Group B included 21 cases in which 17 were having 3rd degree haemorrhoids. The mean operating time of Group A was 52.5 minutes with standard deviation of 11.9 while it was 36.6±9.8 in the other group. The mean blood loss in group A was 51.92ml with standard deviation of 15.68 while it was 70.34±25.59 in group B. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that Ligasure hemorrhoidectomy is a sutureless, closed hemorrhoidectomy technique dependent on a modified electro-surgical unit to achieve tissue and vessel sealing. It is safe and effective, has less blood loss, postoperative pain and complications compared to conventional hemorrhoidectomy.

Corresponding author:

Imam Bakhsh,

Basic Health Unit Akkan Wali District Bahawalnagar

QR code

Please cite this article in press Imam Bakhsh et al., To Compare The Outcome Of Hemorrhoidectomy By Ligasure With Conventional Milligan Morgan's Hemorrhoidectomy., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(10).

INTRODUCTION:

Hemorrhoids, a varicose condition is one of the commonest illnesses which causes per rectal bleeding. The main effective and ultimate treatment for 3rd or 4th degree haemorrhoids is Haemorrhoidectomy. Numerous other procedures have also been practiced, varying from open or closed sharp excision, laser therapy, ultrasonic scalpel dissection to stapled Hemorrhoidectomy. Even though Haemorrhoidectomy is thought to be a small procedure but the complications and the postoperative recovery are very painful to the patient and maybe that's the reason why patients consider haemorrhoidectomy as the last option of treatment¹. Patients as well as surgeons do not like Haemorrhoidectomy because as it is painful for the patient in the same way it is considered to be a difficult procedure among many surgeons².

The main effective and ultimate treatment for 3rd or 4th degree haemorrhoids is Haemorrhoidectomy³. Numerous other procedures have also been practiced, varying from open or closed sharp excision, laser therapy, and ultrasonic scalpel dissection to stapled Hemorrhoidectomy⁴. Even though Haemorrhoidectomy is thought to be a small procedure but the complications and the postoperative recovery are very painful to the patient and maybe that's the reason why patients consider haemorrhoidectomy as the last option of treatment⁵. Traditional Milligan Morgan haemorrhoidectomy is the open surgical procedure in which the haemorrhoid pedicle is ligated by a transfixing suture which may lead to some postoperative complications mostly pain, bleeding and wound infection which ultimately cause prolonged stay in hospital⁶.

Aims and objectives

The basic aim of the study is to compare the outcome of hemorrhoidectomy by LigaSure with conventional Milligan Morgan's hemorrhoidectomy.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross sectional study was conducted in Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during February 2019 to July 2019. This study was conducted with the permission of ethical committee of hospital. There were total 100 patients which were included in this study. All patients with ages between 18 to 70 years of both genders with third and fourth degree Haemorrhoids were included in this study.

Data collection

The patients were divided into two groups. Group A includes Haemorrhoidectomy by Ligasure and group B includes Milligan Morgan Haemorrhoidectomy by using the random allocation. The procedure was carried out with the patient in lithotomy position and a minor reverse Trendelenberg angle. The primary steps in both surgeries were same and consisted of Examination under anesthesia, delivery of hemorrhoids by artery forceps, one applied at the muco cutaneous junction of hemorrhoid, the other at the apex and a skin incision at the base of hemorrhoids and separation of hemorrhoid tissue from the internal sphincter fibers by monopolar diathermy or scissors.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with SPSS software version 20. Independent sample T- test was applied to compare the operative time, blood loss and post-operative pain in both groups. Post stratification Independent Sample T- test was applied; value ≤ 0.05 will be taken as significant.

RESULTS:

The data were collected from 100 patients which can be divided into two groups. The mean age of both groups were 40 to 60 years. Group A included 29 cases in which 20 were having 3rd degree haemorrhoids while Group B included 21 cases in which 17 were having 3rd degree haemorrhoids. The mean operating time of Group A was 52.5 minutes with standard deviation of 11.9 while it was 36.6 \pm 9.8 in the other group. The mean blood loss in group A was 51.92ml with standard deviation of 15.68 while it was 70.34 \pm 25.59 in group B.

Table 01: Comparison of operative outcomes in patients undergoing Ligasure and Milligan Morgan's hemorrhoidectomy.

	<i>Ligasure Group A</i>	<i>Milligan Morgan Group B</i>	<i>P value</i>
Males	09	14	
3RD Degree	20	17	
4th Degree	09	09	
Mean Operative time(minutes)	36.6(9.8)	52.5(11.9)	0.001
Blood loss(in ml)	51.92(15.68)	70.34(25.59)	0.003
Pain score at immediate POD	4.61(0.80)	6.65(0.97)	0.001
Pain score at 1st POD	3.65(0.79)	5.41(0.68)	0.001
Pain score at 7TH POD	1.34(0.56)	2.44(0.68)	0.001
Wound Healing (Appearance of granulation tissue on 14th POD)	24	16	

DISCUSSION:

For symptomatic grade 3 and 4 hemorrhoids, some form of hemorrhoidectomy remains the accepted modality of treatment. The traditional methods like the Milligan Morgan method and the Ferguson's method have been in practice for more than half a century for want of a better alternative. Recent years have seen the introduction of newer techniques with relative merits and demerits⁷. The most significant recent introduction has been the circular stapling device for prolapsed hemorrhoids. This has been criticized for not treating the external component of hemorrhoids and the skin tags. Additionally the stapler cartridges are expensive and beyond the reach of most patients⁸.

About 2 years ago we acquired the Ligasure™ device. It is an electro-surgical device, which is an improved version of bipolar diathermy. It is so effective in achieving hemostasis that it is described as a 'vessel sealing system'. The energy is delivered only to the tissue grasped within the jaws of the hand piece with minimal spread of electrical or thermal energy to adjacent tissues. Complete coagulation of vessels and also tissues is achieved with minimal charring in contrast to conventional diathermy⁹. A computer controlled feedback loop automatically stops the flow of energy when coagulation of the vessels and mucosa is achieved. The vascularized tissue caught between the jaws is reduced to a wafer thin seal, which can be cut across with scissors¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that Ligasure hemorrhoidectomy is a sutureless, closed hemorrhoidectomy technique dependent on a modified electro-surgical unit to achieve tissue and vessel sealing. It is safe and effective, has less blood loss, postoperative pain and complications compared to conventional hemorrhoidectomy..

REFERENCES:

1. Milligan ETC, Morgan CN, Jones LE, Officer R. Surgical anatomy of the anal canal and the operative treatment of hemorrhoids. *Lancet*. 1937;2:1119–1124.
2. Ferguson JA, Heaton JR. Closed hemorrhoidectomy. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 1959;2:176–179.
3. Engel AF, Eijsbouts QA. Hemorrhoidectomy: painful choice. *Lancet*. 2000;355:2253–2254.
4. Wang JY, Lu CY, Tsai HL, Chen FM, Huang CJ, Huang YS, Huang TJ, Hsieh JS. Randomized controlled trial of Ligasure with submucosal dissection versus Ferguson hemorrhoidectomy for prolapsed hemorrhoids. *World J Surg*. 2006;30:462–466.
5. Wang JY, Tsai HL, Chen FM, Chu KS, Chan HM, Huang CJ, Hsieh JS. Prospective randomized controlled trial of Starion™ vs Ligasure™

- hemorrhoidectomy for prolapsed hemorrhoids. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 2007;50:1146–1151.
6. Sayfan J, Becker A, Koltan L. Sutureless closed hemorrhoidectomy: a new technique. *Ann Surg*. 2001;234(1):21–24.
 7. Kwok SY, Chung CC, Tsui KK, Li MKW. A double—blind randomized trial comparing Ligasure™ and Harmonic Scalpel™ hemorrhoidectomy. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 2005;48(2):344–348.
 8. Gentile M, De Rosa M, Pilone V, Mosella F, Forestieri P. Surgical treatment for IV-degree hemorrhoids:LigaSure™hemorroidectomy vs. conventional diathermy. A prospective, randomized trial. *Minerva Chir*. 2011;66(3):207–213.
 9. Khanna R, Khanna S, Bhadani S, Singh S, Khanna A. Comparison of Ligasure Hemorrhoidectomy with Conventional Ferguson’s Hemorrhoidectomy. *Indian J Surg*. 2010;72(4):294–297.doi:10.1007/s12262-010-0192-3.
 10. Palazzo FF, Francis DL, Clifton MA. Randomized clinical trial of Ligasure™ *versus* open haemorrhoidectomy. *Br J Surg*. 2001;89:154–157.